

PACIFICUS

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"I SEE YOU"

I see you when the alarms tear the night,
Your hands begin CPR without delay;
I see you count the hours, guard each sign,
Watching, charting, fighting death each way.

I see you when the pulse returns or not,
When hope hangs thin beneath the sterile light;
I see you stay when families cannot,
And do post mortem care with quiet might.

I see you feed with patience through the tube,
Thick NGTs flushed with practiced, gentle care;
I see you clean the wounds, the sheets, the truth,
And treat each body as a life still there.

I see you bathe them when they cannot move,
You change their diapers, soothe their fragile skin;
You suction secretions so they can breathe,
Doing the work no one applauds within.

I see you check the drips, the rates, the lines,
You question orders, learn the why and how;
I see you study charts, redraw the signs,
Becoming safer, sharper, stronger now.

I see you freeze, then step back in again,
Afraid, yet choosing courage over fear;
I see you learn that healing is not when
We save a life, but stay when death is near.

I see you walk out tired, still you grow,
With aching feet and hearts that feel too full;

Move forward still, there is more you do not know,
But you are already becoming capable.

I see you not just learning how to cope,
But how to care with science and with grace;
And when you doubt, remember this one hope,
I see a nurse in you, not just a face.

